

Fundus Image Analysis to Detect Abnormalities in Diabetic Retinopathy using Computer Aided Design Tools - A Review

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Abstract: Diabetic retinopathy is becoming a major threat to visual loss in human beings. Many researchers are working to develop early detection techniques, which may reduce the risk of vision loss using image-processing techniques like image enhancement and segmentation. Improving the quality of medical images to detect the disease at an early stage is crucial for further medication. It is gaining more focus with automated techniques for machine learning. Filtering and morphological operators enhance image contrast and interested region can be extracted using segmentation techniques from the fundus image of the retina. For feature analysis the optical disk, localization of blood vessels and segmentation are very useful to observe the parameters like area, length and perimeter of blood vessels etc. Algorithms for this analysis include preprocessing, segmentation, feature extraction and classification. This paper tries to give a detailed review of various image-processing methods used in early detection of diabetic retinopathy and future insights to develop algorithms, which reduces clinician's time for diagnosis and pathogenesis.

Keywords: Diabetic retinopathy, Image enhancement, Pre-processing, IRE, Microaneurysm, Segmentation, Feature Extraction, Machine learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) can be classified into two types namely Proliferative and non-proliferative. Abnormal vessel growth (also known as neovascularization) in retina refers to Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (PDR). The early stage of the disease without neovascularization is referred as Non-Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (NPDR). As the disease progress, it may develop into PDR causing severe vision problems, sometimes leading to permanent vision loss too [1]. A high level of blood sugar (known as Hyperglycemia) in humans causes diabetic mellitus like damage to capillaries of the retina. Early signs of diabetic retinopathy are Microaneurysm (small outpunching of retinal capillaries). Microaneurysm rupture and form as hemorrhages inside the retina weakening the vessels and cause fluid to seep into the retina. Fluid deposits under the macula termed as macular edema, which interferes with the normal vision slowly turns into PDR. NPDR is further divided into Early NPDR and Moderate NPDR. At least one Microaneurysm (small outpunching's) present in the retinal exam it gives signs of early NPDR. If more Microaneurysm

present, then cotton wool spots known as Moderate NPDR characterize it and it leads to severe NPDR with venous bleeding and severe Intra-Retinal Micro Vascular Abnormalities (IRMA). Leaking of serum proteins and fatty deposits sometimes appear as cluster of microaneurysm found yellow in color in fundus retinal images and are known as exudates. Accumulation of lipids and proteins in the retina is termed as exudates. So abnormalities in the retinal images include detecting exudates and neovascularization are the useful features for automatic detection. As NPDR progresses, to bypass the damaged vessels, new vessel growth starts which is known as neovascularization. These new vessels are leaky and tenuous or brittle and sometimes misdirected and grow towards the vitreous causing sudden vision loss. Fundoscopy or Ophthalmoscopy allows clinicians to examine the retina, the optic disk and the underlying layer of blood vessels. As the disease progress, the diabetic retinopathy may cause vision loss [1], hence detection at an early stage is crucial. Computer-aided design tools play the major role to detect abnormalities at an early stage and help clinicians for proper diagnosis and treatment within less time [2, 3]. This paper tries to review various methods in literature to detect abnormalities in diabetic retinopathy at an early stage with the help of image processing techniques automatically. The following Fig.1. shows the disease progression from normal retina to proliferative retinopathy.

Fig. 1. Disease progression from the normal retina to the Diabetic retina

II. METHODOLOGY

Ophthalmoscopy or Fundoscopy is used to get the image of an eye in diabetic patients and these images are known as Fundus images. To get clear details of these, images are subjected to image processing techniques.

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In general, various image-processing techniques like image denoising [14], enhancement and segmentation techniques are used to detect abnormalities. Generally, the acquired or captured images are applied to pre-processing techniques to enhance the contrast, brightness of the images, then Interested Region Extraction (IRE) i.e either Microaneurysm or exudates are obtained through segmentation and classification techniques, or the abnormalities can be detected using machine learning algorithms. Predictive modelings is to simplify pathology with the automatic computer-aided diagnosis like pre-processing, segmentation, classification and feature extraction with machine learning and are very much useful in the detection of the disease at an early stage. The general procedure includes pre-processing the acquired fundus image for image enhancement, segmentation and feature extraction for classification to detect abnormalities is given below Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. General Flow of Retinal Image Analysis

Pre-Processing:

Retinal images from Fundoscopy are low contrast in nature and are not useful for detecting abnormalities by segmenting the selected or interested region. Generally available and most commonly used retinal databases are DRIVE (Digital Retinal Images for Vessel Extraction), STARE (Structured Analysis of Retina) DIARETDB (Diabetic Retinopathy Database), HRF (High-Resolution Fundus images database) and Messidor data sets. Fundus images are with poor contrast, non-uniform illumination, and noise. To increase the retinal image contrast, which is acquired from fundus camera many techniques are available in the literature, such as Local Histogram Equalization (LHE), Global Histogram Equalization (GHE) and Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLACHE). Pre-processing aims to highlight the interested region by enhancing the contrast. Various methods like spatial filtering techniques, which works on each pixel with different sizes of masks are available in literature. For enhancement, images from these databases are downscaled to overcome resolution and memory occupancy. Pre-processing steps include green channel extraction, downscaling and contrast enhancement making the image suitable for further processing. The accuracy of segmentation primarily relies on the consistency of the contrast of the entire image. Each pixel has its own importance for medical analysis, so without disturbing the image details contrast has to be increased. Many techniques have been proposed for enhancing low contrast images. Histogram Equalization has its simplicity and good performance in almost all types of images. Histogram Equalization is classified into two classes: Global Histogram Equalization (GHE) and Local Histogram Equalization (LHE) techniques are used to detect lesions of blood vessels

and the presence of optic nerve in the image. Image enhancement techniques magnify the interested region and noise, which causes overshoots. To eliminate overshoots in Laplacian Operator, inverse diffusion equation is used along with self-similarity filtering [6]. Fig. 3 shows enhanced images of diabetic retinopathy with Microaneurysm, blood vessels, and exudates.

Fig. 3. Enhanced images of (a) Microaneurysm, (b) Blood vessels, & (c) Exudates

Denoising the image before segmentation tries to enhance the features at interested region and the performance metric used in pre-processing is mainly to calculate Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) and entropy. Time Domain Constraint Estimator (TDCE) is used calculate the PSNR of the retinal image without losing any details of the retinal image. Intensity information of fundus image is enhanced using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) with help of sub bands of discrete wavelet transform [8], where it calculates entropy as the performance metric and compared with other methods like LHE, GHE, and SVE (Singular Values Equalization). DREAM tries to check the severity in the disease with pre-processing techniques to separate foreground from the retinal image, which consists of candidates or features to observe the severity of the disease [53] with help of spatial filtering to enhance the image. This paper mainly worked on reducing the selected features. In the pre-processing stage acquired images from fundus photography are resized to 256 X 256 or 512 X 512 and the green channel is extracted for more information and to make it clear for further processing.

Morphological operator Dilation is applied on the green channel and Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram equalization (CLACHE) is used to enhance the image. In this paper, pre-processing includes green channel extraction, morphological processing, and contrast enhancement achieved through CLACHE [84]. To get the final pre-processed image, CLAHE image is subtracted from Gray image. Multi score second order Gaussian filters are used to enhance the vessels in pre-processing. As vessels are tiny structures, to get greater enhancement [37] uses Left Invariant rotating Derivative frame [LID], and Locally Adaptive Derivative frame [LAD] are used. The following table gives literature survey on preprocessing for enhancement.

A. Segmentation

Segmentation is a process of subdividing the image into multiple segments as the sets of pixels or super pixels to analyze in computer vision applications. Segmentation is classified into three categories namely Supervised, Unsupervised and Semi-supervised. Supervised segmentation uses priori knowledge whereas unsupervised tries to find patterns of values and to build a probabilistic model to identify

Table- I: Literature survey on pre-processing for image enhancement

Image enhancement	Database	Method	Comments
Satyardi[3],[6]	DRIVE, STARE	Filter based technique's, Gaussian Intensity distribution,	Improves contrast, loss of some image details
Reza et al.[5]	DRIVE, STARE	Adaptive histogram	Improves local contrast as well as noise.
T.Jintasuttisak, S.Intajag [10]	DRIVE, STARE	Histogram-based	Improves contrast of the Green channel, Non-uniform Illumination, amplifies noise too.
Lavanya[13]	DRIVE	Cache filter	Improves tiny structures, computational complexity
Xue et al.[7]	DRIVE, STARE,	Gradient map & (LoG) Laplacian of Gaussian	Local contrast features extracted with phase Congruency
Sarath Chandra[9]	DRIVE, STARE, Pvt. Database	Histogram-based, Contour let transform	Improved PSNR
Miao et.al[11]	DRIVE, STARE	Multiscale top hat transformation, and linear stretching	Improved contrast in two levels, by extracting bright features and optimized
Xiao[12]	DRIVE, Pvt Database	Gamma correction	Gray levels of the green channel are extracted, the global contrast of the image is improved.

The substructures of the interested region in image analysis. Semi-supervised segmentation uses both labeled and unlabeled images of interested regions to identify abnormalities. In Diabetic Retinopathy, IRE may be Microaneurysm (MAs), Exudates (EXs) or Blood Vessels (BVs) and are application oriented.

Segmentation techniques are broadly classified based on an application, as if segmentation based on discontinuities (edge detection), or similarities (finding distance between the similar intensity pixels through connectivity based) using threshold based techniques. Segmentation methods are broadly categorized based on kernels, vessel tracking, thresholding, mathematical morphology and machine learning based [33, 41]. In segmentation process, Kirsch method applied for edge detection, which uses structuring element to find edges through neighbors. As each and every pixel is important to analyze medical images, for post-processing, dilation and erosion applied on segmented images to avoid the false detection of pixels. For retinal image analysis main features used to observe the abnormality are Exudates, Microaneurysm detection and blood vessel detection play crucial role in early detection of the disease.

(a) Microaneurysm (MAs): Microaneurysm is the first sign of visual impairments [16-26], detection of these is a trivial task which is close to blood vessels. Microaneurysm are focal dilatations of retinal capillaries with 10 to 100micro meters. Microaneurysm detection is obtained by calculating size, height, and shape of the peak with a directional cross-sectional profile centered on the local maximum pixel.

Multiscale correlation with dynamic thresholding is used to detect MAs at coarse and fine levels to get candidate selection and true MAs [17]. SVD with contrast enhancement is applied on fundus images and the Hessian-based approach is used for candidate selection. Radon transforms with intensity normalization and SURF are used to locate the exact MAs candidate region [18]. Kernel-based techniques use the concept of vessel profile with intensity variations and also termed as matched filter techniques [13]. The performance metrics are specificity and sensitivity are achieved up to 98.11% and 97.22 % with the confidence level of 0.75. Two types of segmentation methods are used to detect Microaneurysm effectively. They are coarse segmentation using morphological operators and fine segmentation with a Bayes classifier and achieved good results with 99. 9%

accuracy. Locally matching lesion templates are used to detect Microaneurysm from the sub-bands of wavelet-transformed images [19, 25]. The wavelet transform used for MAs detection, here templates are used to match lesions locally from the wavelet sub bands [57, 59]. 90.44% sensitivity is achieved with Genetic algorithm as an optimization technique to select prominent features, which are used to observe abnormality in the given image. [20].

(c)Exudates (Exs): To get effective Exudate detection [28-35] Optical disc in the retinal image has to be eliminated using image segmentation. In paper [30] Exudate detection is achieved with an efficient integrated approach. The methodology includes various steps, first by enhancing the retinal image using Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization, and then Hessian filtering separates blood vessels and the optical disk is identified with the combination of multiresolution analysis. In the remaining image fuzzy K-means, clustering is applied to detect exudates. K means clustering needs to specify the number of clusters and its effectiveness increases with maximum clusters, which in turn increases computational complexity. Exudates with the small radius are very hard to find, so Kirsch method tries to explore the edges in the retinal image. Linde-Buzo-Gray clustering is an improved version of K means algorithm by deriving good codebook for features, which detects the exudates by splitting the clusters but need improvements to find the location of cluster center [33]. This paper finds the bright lesions but fails to identify exudates with a small radius. Retinal image is pre-processed to improve accuracy in exudates detection, Exudate candidate regions are extracted with help of weighted ensembles, and these weights are determined using simulated annealing [34]. A novel approach proposed to get accurate borders of exudates, and exudates are identified using active contour method with the help of grey scale morphology and region wise classifier [35]. (b) Blood Vessels ((BVs): The structural details of blood vessels give maximum information to detect abnormalities in fundus images computer-aided tools. To detect vascular changes in blood vessels, vessels classified into arteries, veins and in turn graph based labels assigned to each vessel segment with the set of intensity features [38, 69].

By computing the geometric mean of the grey image of the diabetic retina, vessel orientation selectivity is achieved from the combination of difference Gaussian filters with unsupervised segmentation of blood vessels. For vessel detection, gradient is computed using different masks like Roberts, Prewitt, and Sobel operators. To describe global vascular structures of retinal blood vessels, intensity-based local features are employed to select the most prominent features with Expectation–Maximization optimization technique. For blood vessel segmentation Matched filter and fuzzy K , and median filters are deployed, and 96.43% sensitivity 76.31% specificity are achieved. Some researchers used Gaussian Intensity Distribution method for vessel segmentation. Blood vessel segmentation achieved with 94% accuracy, 69% sensitivity and 97% specificity using morphological opening and binarization. Optical disc segmentation is achieved using domain knowledge with the low-rank representation of super pixels, and these methods employed for clustering. A new automated method developed to detect blood vessels, which uses directional differential operators to extract the skeleton of main vessel and vessel direction is emphasized using multi directional top-hat operator with rotating structuring element. The vessel information extracted with bit plane slicing and this information is integrated with main skeleton by applying morphological filters and iterative region growing method [86]. To detect the blood vessels, in pre-processing CLACHE algorithm and 2D Gabor filter with morphological reconstruction are used to achieve an average accuracy of 95%. The multi-resolution analysis provides clear details of local binary patterns for texture analysis of blood vessels, which are also termed as uniform with computational simplicity [57]. Images are labeled on four-grade scale and features are extracted by isolating blood vessels, Microaneurysm and hard exudates using SVM to obtain 95% sensitivity. To extract local details with more features from the non-diseased fundus image and these features must be invariant to illumination changes and orientation of pixels. These extracted features from normal image are matched with diseased fundus image to detect abnormalities. Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) is a local descriptor which uses grey scale images for local information based on scale space [82]. The following Fig.4 represents segmentation of (MAs (a), EXs (b) and BVs(c)).

Fig. 4. Enhanced images of (a) Microaneurysm, (b) Blood vessels, & (c) Exudates

B. Feature extraction

Feature is a general term given for an interested region depending on the application used to develop subsequent algorithm and repeatability, robustness, discriminating and independence are its main characteristics. Combination of features forms feature vectors, which were used to encode the

image information. The feature vector includes the statistical parameters like entropy, homogeneity, and Euler number etc., with 64-point DCT [35]. Various features currently used in the literature are shape, color, textural and histogram of an image. As per the abstraction level, they categorized into pixel based, local or global based of an image. [60]. Feature extraction is a process of quantifying the actual information to the desired level and making it adaptable for further processing like classification and detection of abnormalities in the original image for analysis purpose. Feature extraction involves both identifications of relevant features and their selection. To get accuracy in findings, there is a great impact in the selection of local and global features from the image. Shape features are the area, perimeter, thinness ratio, aspect ratio, compactness ratio and elongation or eccentricity ratio. Color features give the contrast details of individual primary colors of Red, Green, and Blue. Histogram features give details of intensity levels of the entire image and their distribution. From the histogram, the following parameters like mean, standard deviation, skewness, energy, and entropy can be computed. Fourier descriptors give spectral details of an image and the parameter power is the primary metric for spectral features. Spectral features used to obtain textural details of the image and are of the function of image size related to the interested region. The texture of interested region has a significant role in medical image analysis and it can be categorized with the use of statistical methods depending on first and second order details like mean, variance, standard deviation, skewness and central moments etc., whereas the first order statistical details can be obtained from histograms. Second order details like correlation, homogeneity, energy and central moments obtained from Gray level co-occurrence matrix and Gray level Difference matrix. These are explained by Haralick to analyze the medical images [54]. Local Binary Pattern (LBP) is very much useful for spectral components and it is invariant texture analysis [59]. Model-based methods try to extract textural features through spatial properties to find the spatial relationships of textural features by using Markov models or Gibbs random models or Gaussian random models [65]. Texture analysis gives a reasonable amount of interested region to identify the abnormalities [53, 55, 57, and 58]. For vessel segmentation, the main categories are filter bank based methods, multiresolution analysis; Gabor filters [23] and Gabor wavelets. Among all Gabor and wavelets provides better information. Filter bank based methods works in frequency and spatial domains by using image transforms [38, 58]. Real-time applications need both frequency and spatial information, so wavelet methods are very much useful [20]. Multiple features may give robust results based on regional characteristics like regional variance, regional gradient, and regional spatial frequency, which explains using the Shearlet transform with the help of sub band coefficients [72, 79 & 82]. While selecting features to classify an image, quality of features and interdependencies between features has gained importance [81, 83 & 85].

Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF) are the framework of multiple scale analysis using convolution and local gradient [84] to extract low level or local features like intensity and orientation [82]. This paper proposed a new ranking method SVM-RFE to observe quality with a reduced computational time with simple distance transform to estimate vessel width as small, medium and large for feature extraction and global intensity information are calculated using statistical measures.

Classification

Classification of retinal images to detect abnormalities is carried out using various classifiers. In supervised learning, the main classifiers are logistic regression and Naive bayes classifiers are linear models, which work with more independent variables. In medical images ground truth images are used to train the classifiers, whereas in unsupervised no ground truth images are available [78]. The main classification algorithms are the nearest neighbor, K-nearest neighbor, nearest centroid, template matching, Bayesian analysis and Neural based. Decision tree classifiers are non-parametric in nature and selection of a suitable classifier improves the classification accuracy. Knowledge-based classification plays a crucial role in medical imaging. The cost function is the measure observing the success rate of classification algorithms. In retinal image classification mostly used cost functions are Specificity (Sp), Sensitivity (Sn), Precision, Accuracy, and F-measure. Table.2 gives different types of supervised and unsupervised classifiers used for retinal image analysis.

Table- II: Types of Classifiers

S.No	Supervised	Un-Supervised
1	Linear Classifiers	Markov random Models
2	Random Forest method	Pattern analysis
3	Support Vector Machine	Fuzzy Clustering
4	Decision Trees	Hierarchical Clustering
5	Gaussian Mixture models	K-means Clustering

It is always good to have ground truth images properly labeled by the clinicians which are used to train the classifier to get good results, like supervised vector machines (SVM), K-means classifiers, GMM models and Ad boost , Nearest neighbors, neural networks, random forest, decision trees and SVM [65] are mostly used classifiers. Many researchers worked on SVM, which outperforms among all the classifiers. Some researchers used neural networks for classification and Bayesian models too. Fuzzy C Means (FCM) clustering and SVM classifier is used to detect Diabetic Retinopathy and achieved Specificity of 95.83%, accuracy of 96.7% with a sensitivity of 100%. For binarizing input retina image line tracking concept is used and a hybrid technique with a combination of Scanning window analysis and Morphology is applied to get reliable results [33]. Neural networks are used for pixel classification and to detect Microaneurysm log Gabor features and Dual-Tree Complex Wavelet Transform are applied, then image feature is extracted by observing the difference between the intensity

levels of the pixel with the pixel at the interested region [32]. This paper explains the local descriptors efficiently and termed as Local Contrast and Ordering (LCO) with higher computational efficiency. In neural networks, features of fundus image are applied as inputs to the number layers and network performance can be increased with a number of inputs, which increases computational cost, hence normalized inputs are used with iterative methods to reduce complexity in the network layers [62].

Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network [MLPNN], is used as a classifier which outperforms and achieves 100% training and cross-validation rates to detect abnormalities in the given image.. Pixel-wise classification is used to identify the maximum number of features from the vessels and the Genetic algorithm is used to optimize the features and achieved an accuracy of 90.2%, sensitivity of 89.6% and specificity of 91.3% respectively [40].

Residual Networks (ResNets) are gaining popularity with minimum feature vectors and little complexity to get better segmentation results. Residual Fully Convolutional Network is proposed to predict segmentation by normalizing medical images with Fully Convolutional networks (FCN)[49], and they iteratively refined. Deep learning [75, 76 & 77] methods are useful for supervised segmentation for retinal blood vessels and an accuracy of 99% and sensitivity of 87% are achieved. Hidden Markov models are an approach to trace the vessels accurately and occlusion handling [50]. The vessels are traced with an accuracy of 95.7% and specificity of 81%. To diagnose PDR, matched filter and modified local entropy thresholding is applied to extract the blood vessels by achieving an average accuracy of 97.6% with Extreme Learning Machine [87]. Enhance K means algorithm is used for blood vessel segmentation and vessel features are extracted with the help of ROI based LBP method. The extracted features were classified by Echo State Neural Network & RBF and achieved an accuracy of 97.95% [88]. To observe global features of an image, histograms are very much useful and sometimes, Histogram distribution of different pixel class overlaps each other, which makes estimation of global parameters inaccurate. Estimation of local parameters with high accuracy is difficult due to inhomogeneity at different regions on spatial scale. To overcome this new method developed to calculate global parameters accurately [89]. One such method is Slope difference distribution for histogram is calculated and then global peaks identified. The local parameters calculated using Gibb’s distribution, which characterizes image as markov model with joint distribution function and achieved good segmentation accuracy with an error rate of 5.7431 when compared to K-means 7.8177. The following Tables 3 and 4 summarizes literature review about various methods used for the analysis of abnormalities in Blood vessels (BV), Exudates (Ex) and Microaneurysm (MA).

Table III Various approaches in segmentation procedures

Paper	Author & Year	Abnormalities			Database	Method	Performance Metrics		
		MA	Ex	BV			Acc	Sp	Sn
Machine learning approach for exudate	Akara.Sophark 2010	MA	Ex	BV	N.A	Naive Bays+ SVM	98.14	92.28	98.52
Automatic Exudate detection	B.Harangi et.al 2012	-	-	Yes	Diaret DB1	Active contour, region wise classifier	NA	NA	NA
Automatic Exudate detection	Wuttichai Laungruang,2014	Yes	Yes	Yes	DIARE TDB	Hessian filtering, Fuzzy c means	NA	NA	NA
Retinal vessel segmentation with ELM	C.Zhu.et al 2017	Yes	Yes	Yes	DRIVE	Phase Congruency & ELM classifier	96.07	98.68	71.4
DREAM	Sohini Choudhury 2014	Yes	Yes	Yes	DRIVE, STARE	-	90	50	100
Optimum Wavelet Transform	G.W name et.al, 2008	Yes	Yes	Yes	Pvt.Database	Wavelets Genetic algorithm	--	--	89.92

Table IV various approaches in segmentation procedures

Paper	Author & Year	Abnormalities			Database	Method	Performance Metrics		
		MA	Ex	BV			Acc	Sp	Sn
Robust hidden Markov model-based intelligent Blood vessel detection	Hassan.M.et al, 2017	-	-	Yes	DRIVE	Hidden Markov models	95.7	81	97
Automatic Detection O Microaneurysm and Haemorrhage's in Colour Eye fundus images	Sérgio Bortolin Júnior and Daniel Welfer	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	CLACHE	92	--	87.6
Blood vessel segmentation in colour fundus images based on regional and Hessian features	Shah SAA, Tang TB, Faye I, Laude A	Yes	Yes	Yes	DRIVE	CLACHE, B-COSFIRE	94.7	--	72.5
Analysis of Retinal Vasculature using a Multiresolution Hermite-Gaussian Model	Li.wang, Abhir Bhale Rao	Yes	Yes	Yes		Morphological operators	97	92	76
Exudate detection in colour retinal images for mass screening of diabetic retinopathy	Xiwei Zhang 2014	Yes	Yes	Yes	E-OpthaEx	Morphology & Random forest	97	93	78

III. CONCLUSIONS

This paper explores various image processing techniques and machine learning algorithms for detecting retinal abnormalities like the growth of abnormal vessels from normal vasculature, small Microaneurysm, and exudates, which may lead to permanent vision loss. Many researchers

worked on pre-processing techniques to brighten the retinal structure for visual quality; still there is an ambiguity in standardizing the methodology to be followed.

As per the state of art, CLACHE technique outperforms in the pre-processing stage to improve contrast details, but a small amount of noise gets amplified and which is not recommended. In the segmentation process, the combination of connectivity based and thresholding techniques outperform with more complexity. In few papers, for classification of abnormality in the diabetic retinal images around 30 to 40 intensity, textural and statistical features observed for proper detection and there are no specific criteria for selecting a number of features to train the classifier. Some researchers used the maximum number of features with optimization techniques to obtain greater accuracy. Still, more work is needed to reduce the number of features to be used and to observe their effectiveness. The genetic algorithm used to optimize the number of features extracted and it is observed that instead of a single classifier, cascaded classifiers and semi-supervised learning outperforms for the given application. Now a day's deep learning, which is a subfield of machine learning, has been emerging as a prominent research area in retinal image analysis due to its effectiveness and less computational complexity. Still, improvements are needed to have accurate algorithms. Microaneurysm detection, Artery and vein classification of retinal images from fundus photography are giving more scope for future directions with proper selection of robust classifiers with suitable segmentation algorithm for computer-aided design. Hybrid methods like pixel-based segmentation with morphological operators are giving better results. This paper may give selection criteria for further research in retinal image analysis.

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It is optional. The preferred spelling of the word "acknowledgment" in American English is without an "e" after the "g." Use the singular heading even if you have many acknowledgments. Avoid expressions such as "One of us (S.B.A.) would like to thank" Instead, write "F. A. Author thanks" *Sponsor and financial support acknowledgments are placed in the unnumbered footnote on the first page.*

REFERENCES

- Gordois A, Cutler H, Pezzullo L, Gordon K, Cruses A, Vineyard S, et al. "An estimation of the worldwide economic and health burden of visual impairment." *Global Public Health*. 2012;7(5):465-481.
- Giancarlo L, Meriaudeau F, Karnowski TP, Li Y, Garg S, Tobin KW, et al. "Exudate-based diabetic macular edema detection in fundus images using publicly available datasets". *Medical Image Analysis*. 2012;16(1):216-226.
- D. Satyarathi, M. R. Kumar, and S. Dandapat," Gaussian intensity distribution modeling of blood vessels in fundus images", *Proceedings of the Annual IEEE India*, 2005.
- K.-Q. Huang, Q. Wang, and Z.-Y. Wu," Natural color image enhancement and evaluation algorithm based on the human visual system", *Computer Vision, and Image Understanding*, 2006(103) pp. 52- 63.
- Reza AM.' Realization of the contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) for real-time image enhancement.' *Journal of VLSI Signal Processing Systems for Signal, Image and Video Technology*. 2004;38(1):35-44
- Rampal H, Kumar RK, Ramanathan B, Das TP." Complex shock filtering applied to retinal image enhancement." In: *Proceedings of the World Congress on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering*. Springer; 2013. p. 900-903.
- Xue W, Mou X, Zhang L, Bovik AC, Feng X. "Blind image quality assessment using joint statistics of gradient magnitude and Laplacian

- feature"s. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*. 2014;23(11):4850-4862.
- Lu Wang, Guohua Liu, Shujun Fu, LingZhong Xu, Kun Zhao, Caiming Zhang, "Retinal Image Enhancement Using Robust Inverse Diffusion Equation and Self-Similarity Filtering".*PLoSOne*, 2016
- P.Sarathchandra, M.C Hanumanth Raju, M.T.Gopalakrishna," Retinal Based Image Enhancement using Contourlet Transform", *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 2014, pp: 581-587
- T.Jintasuttisak, S.Intajag," Color Retinal Image Enhancement by Rayleigh Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization", in 14th International Conference on Control, Automation, and Systems, Korea, 2014, pp. 22-25.
- Miao Liao, Yu-Qian Zhao, Xiao-hong Wang, Pei-shan Dai, Retinal vessel enhancement based on multi-scale top-hat transformation and histogram fitting stretching, *Elsevier*, 2014 pp. 56-62.
- Xiao, Zhitao; Zhang, Xinpeng; Zhang, Fang; Geng, Lei; Wu, Jun; Su, Long; Chen, Liming, "Diabetic Retinopathy Retinal Image enhancement based on Gamma Correction", *Journal of Medical imaging and health informatics*. 2017(7), pp:149-154
- R.Lavanya, P.Mohanaiah," A Hybrid Approach to visual vessel Extraction with Segmentation", *Elsevier, Materials Today*(8), 2018, pp:287-293.
- Ahmad Fadzil.M.Hani et al.," Denoising Methods for Retinal Fundus Images", *IEEE Xplore*, 2014.
- G.Tirupati*, B.Subba Rao, et al. "A Novel Technique for Fundus Image Contrast Enhancement", *International Journal of Bio-Medical Informatics and e-Health*, Volume 2, No.1, 2014
- Jonathan Goh, Lilian Tang et. Al," Evolving the Structure of Hidden Markov models for Microaneurysms detection", *epubs.suvey.ac.uk*, 2010
- B.Zhang, X.Wu, J.You,& F.Karry Detection of microaneurysm using Multiscale correlation coefficients, *Pattern recognition*. Vol.(43), pp:2237-2248,2010.
- K.Adal, S.Ali, D.Sidibe, T.Kamaowski et al, "Automated detection of microaneurysm using robust blob descriptors". *Medical Imaging*, vol.8670, 2013.
- Quellec.G, Mathieu land, et.al." Optimal Wavelet Transform for detection of microaneurysm in Retina Photographs", *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol.27, issue. 2008.
- B.wu, W.Zhu, et al," Automatic detection of microaneurysm in retinal fundus images", *Computer medical imaging & Graphics*, vol.55, pp.: 10-112, 2017.
- Meindert.N.meijer, Bran van Ginneken ET. "AI Retinopathy online challenges: Automatic detection of microaneurysm in digital color fundus photographs", *IEEE Transaction on Medical Image Analysis vol'29, issue1*, pp.: 185-195, 2010.
- T. Walter, P. Massenet et.al, "Automatic detection of microaneurysms in color fundus image, *Medical Image Analysis*, Vol. 11, pp. 555-566. 2017
- Estevan lazar, Andras Hajdu Retinal microaneurysm detection through local rotating cross-section profile analysis", *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol.32, issue 2, 2013
- Carla Peria, Diana Vega, "Using a multi-agent system approach for microaneurysm detection in fundus images", *Artificial Intelligence in medicine*, vol.60: issue 3, pp.17-188, 2014
- Sujay, angadi & Ravi Shankar, "Detection and classification of Microaneurysm using DTCWT and Log Gabor features in Retinal images". Springer, Cham, Print ISBN: 978-3-319-12011-9.2010
- Antal B, Hajdu A, An ensemble-based system for microaneurysm detection and diabetic retinopathy grading. *IEEE Transaction on Biomedical Engineering*. 59:1720-6, 2012
- Leicht S.F. et.al., "Microaneurysm Turnover in Diabetic Retinopathy Assessed by Automated Retmarker DR Image Analysis - Potential Role as a Biomarker of Response to DR Treatment", *Ophthalmologica* 231:198-203, 2014
- Akara Sopharak, "A Simple hybrid method for fine microaneurysm detection from non-dilated diabetic retinopathy retinal images", *Computerized medical imaging and Graphics* vol.137, issue 5-6, pp: 134-402, 2013
- Oliver Faus et al, Algorithms for the Automated Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy Using Digital Fundus Images: A Review. *Journal of Medical Systems*, vol.36, issue 1, pp.: 147-157, 2012
- Wuttichai Luangruangrong, Pusit Kulkasem, Suvanna Rasmeequan, "Automatic Exudate detection in retinal images using efficient integrated approaches". *IEEE Xplore*, 2015.

31. Akara sophark et al, Machine learning approach to Automatic exudate detection in retinal images from diabetic patients, *Journal of Modern Optics*, vol.57, issue 2, 2010.
32. B.Harangi, I.Lazar, A.Hajdes” Automatic exudate detection using active contour model & region classification”, *IEEE Explore*, vol 12, 2012
33. Xiwei Zhang, Guillaume Thibault, Exudate detection in color retinal images for mass Screening of Diabetic Retinopathy, *Medical image analysis Journal*, vol.18, issue 7, pp.: 1026-1043, 2014.
34. P.Prentasic, S.Loncaric, “A Weighted ensemble based automatic detection of exudates in fundus photographs”, *Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC), 36th International Conference IEEE*, 2014
35. Alan.D.Fleming Keith.A.Goatman “The mathematical morphology, the role of hemorrhage & exudate detection in automatic grading Diabetic Retinopathy”, *British Journal of Ophthalmology*, vol.94, issue 6, 2015
36. Feroui Atmel, Messadi Mohammad et al, Improvement of the hard exudate detection method used for computer-aided diagnosis, *International Journal of image, Graphics & Signal Processing*, vol.4, and pp.: 1-27, 2012
37. N. Nimbarte et al. Comparative Analysis of Exudates Detection from Retinal Image with Effective Pre-processing Method, *International Journal on Image & Video Process. ISSN: 2336-0992*, 2015
38. Zhang., Dashthozorg. “Robust retinal vessel segmentation via locally adaptive derivative frames in orientation scores”, *IEEE Transactions in Medical imaging* vol.35(12), 2016.pp. 2631-2644.
39. Argyrios Christodoulidis,” A Multiscale tensor voting approach for small retinal vessel segmentation in high-resolution fundus image”s. *PubMed* 2016.
40. Gaze Pardo, et al, “Trainable COSFIRE filters for vessel delineation with application to retinal images”, *Medical Imaging Annals*, vol.19, issue 1, pp.: 46-57, 2015.
41. Mohammad N. Nobi, Faruk Chowdhury et al, “A New Medical Image Segmentation Technique Based on Variational Level Set Method”, *International Journal of Computer and Electrical Engineering*, Vol. 3, No. 5, 2011.
42. Usman Akram, Ali Aziz et.al Blood vessel enhancement and segmentation using Wavelet Transform. *AI, International Conference on Digital Image processing at Bangkok, Thailand, 2009.*
43. JyothiPrava Dash & Nilamani Bhoi, “A method for blood vessel segmentation in retinal images using morphological operators.”*International Conference on Computer, Electrical & Communication Engineering*, published in *IEEE*, 2016
44. S. Supot, C. Thanapong, P. Chuchart, and S. Manas, “Automatic segmentation of blood vessels in the retinal image based on fuzzy K-median clustering”, pp. 584–588, *IEEE*, Shenzhen, 2007.
45. D. Marín, A. Aquino et al., “A new supervised method for blood vessel segmentation in retinal images by using gray-level and moment invariants-based features”, *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 146–158, 2011.
46. B.Dashbozorog, “An automatic graph-based approach for artery /vein classification in retinal images”, *IEEE Transactions on Image processing*, vol; 23, issue 3, pp.: 1073-1083, 2014.
47. J.I.Orlando, M.B.Blaschko,” Learning fully connected CRF’s for blood vessel segmentation in retinal images”, *Medical image computing & Computer-assisted intervention, lecture notes in computer science. Springer* pp.634-641, 2014
48. L. Liskowski, K.Krawiec, “Segmenting retinal blood vessels with deep neural networks”, *IEEE Transactions in Medical Imaging* vol.35 issue.11, pp.: 2369-2380. 2016
49. Cheng Zang, Zhu et al,” Retinal vessel segmentation in color fundus images using extreme learning machine”, *Computerised Medical Imaging & Graphics*, vol.355, pp.: 68-77, 2017.
50. M.Hassan, Amin.M,” Robust Hidden Markov models based on intelligent blood vessel detection of fundus images”, *Computer methods and programs in Biomedicine*, vol.151, pp.: 13-201, 2017
51. M.D. Zeiler, Fergus, “Visualizing and Understanding Convolutional Networks”, *European Conference on Computer Vision*, pp.: 818-833, Springer 2014.
52. Ketki S. Arcade’, Kshitija A et al., “Automatic Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy using Image Processing and Data Mining Techniques”, *International Conference on Green Computing and Internet of Things, IEEE*, 2015
53. Sohini roychowdauri, “DREAM: Diabetic Retinopathy Analysis Using Machine Learning, *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, Vol. 18, NO. 5, 2014
54. Ananth madabhushi, Image analysis and machine learning in digital pathology: Challenges and Opportunitie”s, Ananth madabhushi, *Medical image analysis*, 2016
55. Ali Ahmadvand and Mohammad Reza Daliri, “A Review on Texture Analysis Methods” in *Biomedical Image Processing, OMICS Journal of Radiology, OMICS J Radiol* 5:2, 2016.
56. Haralick, R.M, Shanmugam K et al., “Textural features for image classification, *Systems”, Man and Cybernetics, IEEE transactions* pp: 610-621, 1973.
57. Ojala T, Pietikainen M, Maenpaa T, “Multiresolution Gray-scale, and rotation invariant texture classification with local binary patterns”. *Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence IEEE Transactions on* 24: pp: 971-987, 2002
58. Ahmadvand A, Kabiri P,” Multispectral MRI image segmentation using Markov random field mode”l. *Signal, Image and Video Processing* 10: pp: 251-258, 2016
59. Ahmadvand A, R, Hajiali MT, Mosavi MR,” A novel LBP method for invariant texture classification”. In *Second International Conference on Knowledge-Based Engineering and Innovation (KBEI)* pp.: 152-157, 2015
60. Ahmadvand A, Daliri MR, “Rotation Invariant Texture Classification using Extended Wavelet Channel Combining and LL Channel Filter Bank”. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 2016
61. Bhateja V, Patel H et al,” Multimodal Medical Image Sensor Fusion Framework Using Cascade of Wavelet and Contourlet Transform Domains”, *Sensors Journal* 15: pp:6783-6790, 2015.
62. Michael Drozdal et al”, Learning normalized inputs for iterative estimation in medical image segmentation”, *Medical Image Analysis, Vol.44*, 2018
63. M.M El.Gayar, “A Comparative study of image low-level feature extraction algorithms”. 2013
64. Lee.wang et.al ,”Analysis of Retinal Vasculature using a Multiresolution Hermite-Gaussian model”, *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*.
65. Harini.R & Sheela.N, “Feature extraction and classification of retinal images for automated detection of Diabetic Retinopathy”, *Cognitive computing, and information processing, 2nd International IEEE conference* 2016 .
66. Parth Panchal & Tejendra Panchal “An algorithm for Retinal feature extraction using the Hybrid approach”, *Procedia, Computer Science Vol 79*.2016.
67. Enrique.V.Carrera. et.al “Automated detection of diabetic retinopathy using SVM”, *Published in IEEE Xplore*. 2017.
68. F.-L. Yi and W.-H. Xu, “Segmentation of blood vessels in color fundus images based on optimal multi-threshold method”, *Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning and Cybernetics (ICMLC '12)*, vol. 2, pp. 725–728, *IEEE*, 2012
69. Malak.T.Buntan,” Auto-segmentation of retinal blood vessels using Image processing”, DOI: 10.110/KACSTIT, Published in *IEEE Xplore*, 2016.
70. Xu Y, Duan L, Lin S, et.al,” Optic cup segmentation for glaucoma detection using low-rank super pixel representation”, 2010
71. Jingyun duo et .al,” LCO: A robust and efficient local descriptor for image matching”, 2016
72. Xian Liu, Yue Zhou, Jiazun. “Image fusion based on shearlet transform and regional features”, *International Journal of Electronics & Communication Vol.68.Issue 6* 2013
73. Amole Prataprao Bhatkar, G.U.Karat, “Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy in Retinal Images Using MLP Classifier”, *IEEE Xplore*, 2016.
74. Xian Zhou, Jiajun Wang,” Feature Selection for Image Classification Based on a New Ranking Criterion”, *Journal of Computer and C Zhang. Dashthozorg. Communications*, vol.3, pp: 74-79, 2013
75. Fan Huang, Bar.M.Ter. “Retinal artery/vein classification using genetic search feature selection”, *Computer methods & programs in Biomedicine*, vol.161, pp.: 197-207., 2018
76. K.K.Maini, J.put.Tuset, *Deep retinal image understanding, Medical image computing & Computer Assisted Intervention, Springer*, and pp: 140-148.2016
77. I. Good fellow, Y.Benzio,” *Deep Learning*”, MIT press 2016.
78. Zhee. Zhou, et al., Zhee, Zhoy, et al., “Unsupervised segmentation of neutral images based on statistical modeling, *Neuro Computing*”, vol.252, pp: 95-101, 2017
79. Ma, J., Sheridan, R. P., Liaw, A., Dahl, G. E. & Svetnik ,”Deep neural nets as a method for quantitative structure-activity relationships”, *V. J. Chem. Inf. Model.* 55, 263–274 2015

80. MESSIDOR: Digital Retinal Images.
<http://messidor.crihan.fr/download-en.php>.
81. Emanuele Trucco, Alfredo Ruggeri et.al. "Validating Retinal Fundus Image Analysis Algorithms: Issues & purpose", Investigating Ophthalmology and Visual Science, vol.54, pp: 3546-3559, 2013.
82. Jian Wu, Zhiming cue et.al, A comparative study of SIFT and its invariants, Measurement Science Review, vol, 13. Issue.3, 2013.
83. Dawn.A.sim, Pearce.A.Kaene et.al "Automatic Retinal Image Analysis for Diabetic retinopathy in Telemedicine", Springer, March 2015
84. Eduoard Oyallan, Julin Rabin, An analysis of SURF method, Image Processing Online, 5, pp. 176-218. 2015
85. Kirsty Tardon et.al," A review of feature-based retinal image analysis, Expert review of Ophthalmology", vol.12, issue3. 2017.
86. M.Fraz M .Basit A, Barman. S, "Application of morphological bit planes in retinal blood vessel extraction", Journal of Digital Imaging, 2013,26(2) PP: 274-286.
87. Bala.M.Ponni, Vijayachitra.S," Extraction of retinal blood vessels and diagnosis of Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy using Extreme Learning Machine", Journal of medical Imaging and Health Informatics, 2015, vol 5, pp:248-256.
88. Nidhi.M.Tamil, Gunasekharan.K , "Efficient Ranking of Diabetic Retinopathy & Glaucoma using Echo State Neural Network and Radial Basis function,"Journal of medical Imaging and Health Informatics, 2016, vol 6, pp: 869-874.
89. Wang, Zhen Zhou ," Image segmentation by combining global & local properties" Expert Systems with Applications, 2017, vol 87, pp:30-40.

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